

“A study to evaluate the effect of laughter therapy in reducing distress among patients undergoing treatment for cancer in selected hospital at mangaluru”

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ABSTRACT: Cancer occurs due to abnormal growth of the cell in the body. The diagnosis and treatment of the disease leads to various physical, psychological, social and spiritual distress. The current study was conducted to evaluate the effect of laughter therapy in reducing distress among patients undergoing treatment for cancer. A quantitative approach was adopted to evaluate the effectiveness of laughter therapy. The investigator selected quasi experimental one group pretest - post-test design. Probability simple random sampling technique through lottery method was used to select the required number of samples. The investigator assessed the distress level through interview method by using sociodemographic variables and standardized tool of NCCN distress thermometer. Laughter therapy was administered by the investigator and booklet was provided. After a week of administration of laughter therapy, post-test was done using the same instrument. The pre-test score of the present study showed that among 60 samples 45 (75%) samples experienced moderate distress, 8 (13%) samples experienced extreme distress, 7 (12%) samples experienced mild distress and none of the samples experienced no distress. Whereas, in the post test result reveals that out of 60 samples 42 (70%) samples had mild distress, 13 (22%) experienced moderate distress, 5 (8%) samples had no distress and none of the samples experienced extreme distress. The percentage of enhancement score was 43.5% after the administration of laughter therapy. In the post test, after the administration of laughter therapy significant improvement was seen in the areas of physical, emotional, social, practical, spiritual and other concerns. The effectiveness of laughter therapy in reducing distress was evaluated by using paired ‘t’ test and the obtained value 19.13 was greater than table value at $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the study concluded that the laughter therapy was effective in reducing distress among patients undergoing treatment for cancer.

Keywords: Effect; laughter therapy; distress; patients undergoing treatment for cancer.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer is emerging as a public health problem around the world. According to the World Health Organization, cancer has caused 24.8% stress, 24% depression, and 24% anxiety, among the patients receiving cancer treatment that affecting patients on their physiological, social, and psychological levels. Different studies have shown that the practice of laughter therapy is the best alternative mean for reducing distress among patients undergoing treatment for cancer.

Laughter brings measurable physiological changes like oxygen levels in the blood, muscle relaxation, blood circulation, and the release of certain hormones in the body. The nervous system in the human body gets stimulated by laughter, which triggers the electrical impulses in the brain to start up chemical reactions, including the release of natural tranquilizers, pain relievers, and endorphins, helping to tackle their depression, physical stress, and mental stress, boost the immune system, promote a positive outlook, manage pain, maintain blood pressure, increase self-confidence.

METHODOLOGY

Research approach

In the current study quantitative approach was used

Research Design

Quasi-experimental one group pretest and posttest design

Sampling Technique

Probability simple random sampling technique with lottery method was used to select the study samples.

Research design

The investigator selected a quasi-experimental one-group pre and post-test design to evaluate the effect of laughter therapy in reducing distress among patients undergoing treatment for cancer.

Figure 4.2 Research design

- O₁: Assessment of pre-test level of distress by using standardized NCCN distress thermometer scale among patients undergoing treatment for cancer.
 X: Administration of laughter therapy for reducing distress among patients undergoing treatment for cancer.
 O₂: Assessment of post-test level of distress by using standardized NCCN distress thermometer scale among patients undergoing treatment for cancer.

Group	Day 1	Treatment	Day 7
Distressed patients undergoing treatment for cancer	O ₁	X	O ₂

Research setting

The study was conducted in Yenepoya Medical College Hospital at Mangaluru. The hospital has a well-equipped oncology department, which is divided into medical and surgical oncology units. Around 60 patients are treated daily in the oncology inpatient department and daycare settings. Staff in the oncology wards were supportive for the conduction of the study and patients showed interest to learn and practice the intervention provided.

Sample

The current study sample consists of patients who are distressed due to diagnosis and treatment modalities of cancer in Yenepoya Medical College Hospital at Mangaluru.

Plan for data analysis

Data analysis was done based on the objectives and hypotheses of the study.

- The collected demographic data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean, percentage, and frequency.
- Paired 't' test was used to evaluate the effectiveness of laughter therapy.
- The X² (Chi-square) test was used to find the association with various demographic variables.

RESULTS

The result chapter deals with the analysis and interpretation of collected data from 60 samples to evaluate the effect of laughter therapy in reducing distress among patients undergoing treatment for cancer which involves computation of certain measures related to studies.

Objectives of the study

- To assess the level of distress among patients undergoing treatment for cancer.
- To administer laughter therapy among patients undergoing treatment for cancer.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of laughter therapy to reduce distress among patients undergoing treatment for cancer.
- To find out the association of posttest level of distress among cancer patients with selected sociodemographic variables such as age, gender, religion, marital status, education, occupation, family income, type of family, co-morbid illness, type of treatment, and duration of cancer treatment.

Hypotheses

All the hypotheses are tested at a 0.05 level of significance

H₁ – There was a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test level of distress among patients undergoing treatment for cancer.

H₂ – There was a significant association between the distress level of cancer patients with selected sociodemographic variables such as age, gender, religion, marital status, education, occupation, family income, type of family, duration of cancer, co-morbid illness and type of treatment of cancer.

Table 1 Overall comparison of pre-test and post-test distress level among patients undergoing treatment for cancer.

Table 1 reveals that in the pre-test score the majority of the samples 45 (75%) experienced moderate distress, 8 (13%) samples experienced extreme distress, 7 (12%) were under mild distress and none of the samples were under the category of no distress. Whereas in the post-test score majority of samples 42 (70%) had mild distress, 13 (22%) had moderate distress, 5 (8%) had no distress and none of the samples experienced extreme distress. The study concluded that the distress level among patients undergoing cancer treatment was reduced after the administration of laughter therapy.

N = 60

Sl. No.	Levels of distress	Pre-test		Post test	
		Percentage		Percentage	
		Frequency (N)	(%)	Frequency (N)	(%)
1.	No distress	0	0	5	8

2.	Mild distress	7	12	42	70
3.	Moderate distress	45	75	13	22
4.	Extreme distress	8	13	0	0

Figure 1 Overall comparison of pre-test and post-test distress level among patients undergoing treatment for cancer

Figure 1 shows that in pre-test majority of samples experienced moderate distress. Whereas, after the administration of laughter therapy samples experienced mild level of distress.

Table 2 Area-wise distribution of pre-test distress level among patients undergoing treatment for cancer

In the table, 2.2 mean pretest distress level and mean percentage scores in the 6 different domains among 60 samples undergoing cancer treatment are depicted. The mean score of distress level under emotional concerns with standard deviation was 2.08 ± 0.18 and the mean score percentage was 23. The mean distress for physical concern with standard deviation was 1.91 ± 2.76 and the mean score percentage was 21. The mean score of distress level for spiritual concern and standard deviation was 1.2 ± 0.004 and mean score percentage was 20. The mean score among social concerns with a standard deviation was 1.18 ± 0.018 and mean score percentage was 19. The mean and standard deviation for practical concern was 1.88 ± 0.154 and mean score percentage was 15. The mean distress level for the category of other problems with standard deviation was 0.15 ± 0.014 and mean score percentage of which was 15. The overall pretest mean score for distress level among 60 samples and standard deviation was 8.4 ± 3.13 and mean score percentage was 18. The area-wise pretest distress level describes that the emotional concerns among the samples was 23%, in which 30 samples experienced the loss of interest and 20 samples experienced grief. Whereas physical concern was 21%, 20 samples experienced sleeping pattern disturbance and 20 samples experienced fatigue.

N=60

S. No.	Areas	Max. Score	Mean Score	SD	Mean Score Percentage (%)
1	Physical Concern	9	1.91	2.76	21
2	Emotional Concern	9	2.08	0.18	23
3	Social concern	6	1.18	0.018	19
4	Practical concern	12	1.88	0.154	15
5	Spiritual concerns	6	1.2	0.004	20
6	Other problems	1	0.15	0.014	15

Overall 43 8.4 3.13 18

Figure 2 Area-wise distribution of pre-test distress level among patients undergoing treatment for cancer

Figure 2 shows that among 60 samples emotional concern was found to be high before giving laughter therapy.

Table 3 Area-wise distribution of post-test distress level among patients undergoing treatment for cancer

In table 3 mean post-test distress level and mean percentage scores in the 6 different domains among 60 samples undergoing cancer treatment are depicted. The mean distress level regarding the physical concern and standard deviation was 1.55 ± 0.045 and the mean score percentage was 17. The mean distress level among social concern and its standard deviation was 0.87 ± 1.22 and the mean score percentage was 14. The mean distress level for spiritual concern and standard deviation was 0.52 ± 0.23 and the mean score percentage was 8. The mean distress level under practical concern and standard deviation were 0.93 ± 0.005 and the mean score percentage was 7. The mean distress level for other problems with standard deviation was 0.1 ± 0.014 and the mean score percentage was 10. The overall post-test mean distress level score and standard deviation were 5.12 ± 1.52 among 60 samples with a mean score percentage of 12.

N = 60

S. No.	Areas	Max. Score	Mean Score	SD	Mean Score Percentage (%)
1	Physical Concern	9	1.55	0.045	17
2	Emotional Concern	9	1.15	0.003	12
3	Social concern	6	0.87	1.22	14
4	Practical concern	12	0.93	0.005	7
5	Spiritual concerns	6	0.52	0.23	8
6	Other problems	1	0.1	0.014	10
	Overall	43	5.12	1.52	12

Figure 3 Area-wise mean and mean percentage of post-test distress level among patients undergoing treatment for cancer

Figure 3 describes that there was a significant improvement in the post-test level of physical concerns 17% and emotional concern 12% after administering laughter therapy.

Table 4 Effectiveness of laughter therapy on distress level among patients undergoing treatment for cancer.

Table 4 explains that the pre-test mean and standard deviation distress level among patients undergoing cancer treatment was 7.06 ± 1.98 , which was reduced in the post-test showing the mean and standard deviation of 2.71 ± 1.76 . Their mean difference was 4.35 showing a 43.5% improvement in mean score percentage. This shows that the mean post-test distress level score was significantly lower than the mean pre-test level distress. The calculated 't' value = 19.13 was greater than the table value at $p < 0.05$ level of significance. The study concludes that Laughter therapy was found to be effective in reducing distress among patients undergoing cancer treatment was effective. Hence, the research hypothesis H_1 was accepted.

N = 60

S. No	Variables	Mean	Mean Percentage	Standard deviation	Mean difference	Enhancement of mean score percentage	t value
1	Pre-test	7.06	70.6	1.98	4.35	43.5%	19.13
2	Post test	2.71	27.1	1.76			

Figure 4 Effectiveness of laughter therapy on distress level among patients undergoing treatment for cancer

Figure 4 shows significant difference in mean and mean percentage with effective level of enhancement score of 43.5%.

Table 5 Association between post-test level of distress among patients undergoing treatment for cancer with sociodemographic variables

Table 5 explains that there was no significant association found between the post-test distress level of cancer patients and sociodemographic variables such as age, gender, religion, marital status, education, occupation, family income, type of family, duration of cancer, co-morbid illness and type of treatment of cancer. Hence, the research hypothesis H_2 was rejected and null hypothesis H_0 was accepted.

N =60							
Variables	No distress	Mild	Moderate	Extreme	df	χ^2 value	Inference
1. Age in years							
<35	1	10	2	0			
35-45	0	6	5	0	9	6.078	NS
45-55	2	11	2	0			
>55	2	15	4	0			
2. Gender							
Male	3	25	7	0			
Female	2	17	6	0	3	0.138	NS
3. Religion							
Hindu	2	27	10	0			
Christian	0	0	0	0			
Muslim	3	15	3	0	9	2.927	NS
Others	0	0	0	0			
4. Marital status							
Married	5	33	11	0			
Unmarried	0	6	1	0	9	1.732	NS
Widow/widower	0	3	1	0			
Separated	0	0	0	0			
5. Education							
No education	1	17	3	0			
Primary	1	9	4	0	12	6.89	NS
Secondary	1	13	5	0			
Graduation	2	3	1	0			
Post-graduation	0	0	0	0			
Variables	No distress	Mild	Moderate	Extreme	df	χ^2 value	Inference
6. Occupation							
Unemployed	1	19	6	0			
Student	0	3	0	0	9	10.03	NS
Public	0	1	0	0			
Private	4	19	7	0			
7. Family income							
<15000	2	10	3	0			
15-30000	2	31	10	0	6	5.02	NS
>30000	1	1	0	0			
8. Family type							

Nuclear	3	19	5	0			
Joint family	1	15	5	0	6	0.91	NS
Extended family	1	8	3	0			
9. Duration of illness							
<3months	1	16	7	0			
3-12 months	2	22	5	0	6	5.47	NS
>12 months	2	4	1	0			
10. Co-morbid illness							
No illness	5	33	11	0			
DM/HTN	0	6	6	0	6	2.32	NS
Others	0	7	4	0			
11. Type of treatment							
Surgery	2	3	13	0			
Radiation	0	2	1	0	15	13.63	NS
Chemotherapy	1	1	13	0			
Both B & C	1	1	8	0			
All the above	1	6	7	0			

*S=Significant; NS=Not significant

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Disclaimer

The views and inferences expressed in this publication are those of author's.

Conflicts of interest

None declared

Abbreviations used

CAM	=	Complementary and alternative medicine
ICMR	=	Indian Council of Medical Research
NCCN	=	National Comprehensive Cancer Network
PRS	=	Patient-reported Symptoms
SD	=	Standard Deviation
SDT	=	Symptoms Distress Thermometer
STAI-S	=	State Trait Anxiety Inventory – S

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